

Spatial analysis of economic opportunities and outcomes in rural Scotland: an assets-based approach

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Authors: Jonathan Hopkins, Leonie Schulz, Nick Roxburgh, Margaret McKeen

Social, Economic and Geographical Sciences Department, The James Hutton Institute, Craigiebuckler, Aberdeen

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Highlights

This research is part of the project “Informing a socially and spatially just future for the Scottish rural economy: pinpointing opportunities, assets and support needs” led by the James Hutton Institute¹. As part of this project, we have created and analysed a novel and spatially detailed dataset of demographic and economic outcomes and diverse assets which can, through further analysis, support economic opportunities and development in rural areas.

The spatial and Scotland-wide approach taken in this research provides new insights into rural inequalities by producing valuable, local-level data and evidence on changing economic opportunities and inequalities in rural Scotland.

What did we do?

We calculated indicators of rural development for a hexagonal grid (cell size: 5km) covering the entire land area of Scotland. The gridded dataset represents novel and valuable information, which is available at a consistent and granular geography.

These data were used to provide an up-to-date overview of the uneven demographic and economic changes in Scotland, identifying inequalities in the distribution of economic development resources across the country. We identified themes of economic assets and correlations between these, and explored the predictors of longer-term changes in local outcomes in rural Scotland. This spatially detailed and thematically broad database of indicators makes a considerable contribution to the evidence base on rural development and spatial inequalities in Scotland.

What did we learn?

Our approach has allowed us to provide an up-to-date and longitudinal overview of the uneven demographic and economic changes in Scotland, and the inequalities in the distribution of economic development resources across the country. Using an ‘assets’ approach to understand rural economic opportunities has, alongside a granular and consistent measurement framework, proved to be useful in identifying development strengths, weaknesses and inequalities in Scotland, and these data resources are well suited to further, customised analyses on demographic, social and economic changes. Some key findings are:

- Rural demographic challenges are increasing and accelerating, especially in remoter and sparsely populated areas, although with notable local-level variability between longer-term 'entrenched' population declines and population growth in some rural areas. The size of recent changes in the local population, the persistence of population declines and imbalances, and the corresponding economic trends, could inform variable and place-based policy approaches and the design of different population policy targets in rural Scotland.
- The distributions of economic assets across rural Scotland - and changes in these - show diverse patterns. The apparent 'over-representation' of some types of services in remoter rural areas, relative to their population, does not appear to be a predictor of positive outcomes. Essential health and care services and rural schools have declined in number in recent years.
- How meaningful accessibility to assets and services should be measured in rural areas is a critical, difficult, and ongoing question. The large proportion of Scotland's population which lives in urban areas, accompanied by extensive sparsely- and non-populated areas, create particular complexities: the statistics based on aggregations of gridded data in this report are a relatively simple and pragmatic approach, but are only one possible way of measuring accessibility.
- Regression analyses have identified significant predictors of key outcomes - changes in the working age and employed populations - for contrasting types of rural areas. These should be interpreted with caution, but identify positive effects of assets reflecting care and charities, and potentially nuanced influences of tourism and foundational economic activities.

¹ This project forms part of the Environment, Natural Resources and Agriculture 2022-27 research programme. The project uses mixed methods to create an advanced, holistic understanding of the Scottish rural economy to identify and inform better interventions and approaches to local development which can enable positive changes in communities.

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Context

The Scottish Government funds a programme of strategic research through the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services (RESAS) Division to advance the evidence base in the development of rural affairs, food and environment policies.

One of the themes of the research programme is Theme E, Rural Futures. This theme has three research topics: rural communities, rural economy and land reform. There are two projects within each topic led by Scotland's Rural College and the James Hutton Institute. This publication sits within the Rural Economy topic of this theme. Within the rural economy topic, the two projects are:

- Informing a socially and spatially just future for the Scottish rural economy: pinpointing opportunities, assets and support needs
- Novel insights on Scotland's rural and island economies

The first project, led by the James Hutton Institute, aims to use mixed methods to create an advanced, holistic understanding of the Scottish rural economy and the diversity of responses to multiple crises and events across rural Scotland, in the context of national objectives to deliver a wellbeing economy and longer-term challenges of inequality and depopulation. We aim to identify and inform better interventions and approaches to local development which can enable positive changes in communities. This project will produce evidence, including written publications, open datasets, and online material available to all.

Background and aims

The research described in this report was carried out within the 'Rural Futures' theme of the Scottish Government's Strategic Research Programme (2022-27). The broader aim of the research project is to create an advanced, holistic understanding of the Scottish rural economy, and this work contributes to this by creating and analysing a novel and spatially detailed dataset of demographic and economic outcomes, and diverse assets which can support economic opportunities and development in rural areas.

This work has been informed by key strategies and policies of the Scottish Government, including its goal of a wellbeing economy²; and its vision of this as "Thriving across economic, social and environmental dimensions" noted in the National Strategy for Economic Transformation³. This multi-dimensional view is an acknowledgement of the limitations of traditional economic metrics for understanding meaningful development (Costanza et al., 2009), which is also recognised by the thematically broad way that economic progress is understood in Scotland through the National Performance Framework⁴ and is reflected in the multi-dimensional objectives of the National Islands Plan⁵ and the statement that several factors and policy areas are relevant to long-term population challenges within the Addressing Depopulation Action Plan⁶. Despite these goals, key data used to measure economic development - the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation - has acknowledged limitations for understanding rural deprivation (Clelland and Hill, 2019), and the locations of essential economic services are not well understood (MacKinnon et al., 2022). This research also takes place at a time of high economic inequality (McCann, 2020) with places being left behind economically and in other ways (Pike et al., 2023).

The spatial and Scotland-wide approach taken in this research, of measuring access to several categories of economic assets - the resources of people and places which can be accessed and used to benefit businesses and communities - aimed to produce new, valuable, local-level data and evidence on changing economic opportunities and inequalities in rural Scotland, at a time of major events and uncertainties affecting Scotland's economy and communities as a whole, and long-term demographic challenges affecting many communities.

The spatially detailed, consistently measured, and thematically broad database of indicators created in this research makes a considerable contribution to the evidence base on rural development and spatial inequalities in Scotland. It

² <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-wellbeing-economy/>

³ <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-national-strategy-economic-transformation/>

⁴ <https://webarchive.nrsotland.gov.uk/20250311153900/https://nationalperformance.gov.scot/about/what-it>

⁵ <https://www.gov.scot/publications/national-plan-scotlands-islands/>

⁶ <https://www.gov.scot/publications/supporting-enabling-sustainable-communities-action-plan-address-depopulation/>

also aligns closely with the goals of the Government Statistical Service’s subnational data strategy⁷ which recognises the data gaps which restrict a fuller understanding of spatial inequalities within the UK. In this report, we use these data to provide an up-to-date and longitudinal overview of the uneven demographic and economic changes in Scotland, and the inequalities in the distribution of economic development resources across the country. Secondly, we create measures of rural diversity by identifying dimensions which underpin and summarise the current accessibility of economic development resources across Scotland; identify rural places with high access to these different types of assets; and investigate the correlations between these. And thirdly, we investigate which types of assets, and changes in assets, are associated with longer-term changes in key demographic and economic outcomes in rural Scotland.

[Prioritising and calculating aspects of rural economic development: summarising previous research](#)

The view that diverse and multi-dimensional factors can contribute to wellbeing and development is recognised in existing frameworks defined by researchers and policymakers, which often describe and refer to multiple ‘capitals’. Examples include the ‘four capitals’ (business, community, environment, people) identified by the Advisory Group on Economic Recovery⁸ in Scotland as contributing to wellbeing and resilience and the group of ‘community capitals’ (natural, cultural, human, social, political, financial, built) supporting sustainable communities (Flora et al., 2018).

In this research, we identified priority categories of assets for analysis by engaging with stakeholders and practitioners involved in rural economic development in Scotland about the resources held by people and places which are required to support a wellbeing-focused economic recovery in rural and island communities. An early ‘inventory’ was created⁹ following structured workshop discussions in 2023. The suite of assets which emerged (Figure 1) correspond with essential services and infrastructure, third sector activities, human capital, social and community infrastructure, natural and cultural capital, the abilities of local people, and economic activities which correspond with some of the ‘growth sectors’ defined by the Scottish Government as national priorities¹⁰ - these include energy, food and drink, and tourism. Following this, a range of predominantly open datasets have been analysed to identify the geographical locations of several of these assets, as well as a series of demographic and economic outcome variables. An update on this work in 2024 identified highly uneven patterns of infrastructure developments (renewable energy and fast internet access) and diversity in demographic change in remoter regions. These trends are recognised within the analysis of the refined and finalised data on rural assets and outcomes which is outlined in this report.

⁷ <https://analysisfunction.civilservice.gov.uk/policy-store/gss-subnational-data-strategy/>

⁸ <https://www.gov.scot/publications/towards-robust-resilient-wellbeing-economy-scotland-report-advisory-group-economic-recovery/>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8121405>

¹⁰ https://www.gov.scot/binaries/content/documents/govscot/publications/statistics/2019/07/industry-statistics/documents/industry-statistics-database/industry-statistics-database/govscot%3Adocument/Industry_Statistics_Database.xlsx

Figure 1: Categories and types of assets prioritised in this research

Assessing economic indicators using a gridded approach

The final indicators which have been analysed within this report have been calculated for a consistent, spatially detailed grid of small hexagonal cells (width: 5km, 4,529 cells) covering Scotland. This geography is described in more detail below. The indicators which have been produced in this research, representing types of economic assets and forms of demographic and economic outcomes, are summarised below (Table 1). These were calculated at the grid cell level by extracting, processing and analysing a large volume of spatial, administrative and demographic datasets (Appendix 1). These datasets include official statistics and information published by the Scottish and UK Governments and by official regulatory bodies; Census population totals and associated geographies; volunteered geographical information in OpenStreetMap; environmental designations and land cover; and a detailed dataset on property sales provided by RightMove. Depending on the format of the input datasets, estimated indicator values at the grid level were created using different methods, including:

- Reliable population and Census datasets, published at the level of small geographies (e.g. Output Areas) in Census years (1991, 2001, 2011, 2021-2), were ‘downscaled’ to the grid cell level through reallocation, using highly granular data on the locations of people (for c. 90m cells) for similar years.
- Non-geographical datasets – for example, the addresses of facilities, businesses or other features, were spatialised through address geocoding, matching these features to the locations of postcodes, settlements, parts of settlements and islands.
- OpenStreetMap is a global database of volunteered geographical information, reflecting crowd-sourced mapping and other processed datasets. The quality and completeness of this form of information has been questioned, as “data contributors are not necessarily experts” (Moradi et al., 2021: 181). In this work, data from OpenStreetMap has been used to identify the locations of features where these are missing (schools) and has been combined with other datasets to maximise completeness (grocery stores). Quality controlled and processed data from OpenStreetMap has been used to identify the recent presence of assets (e.g. places for social eating and drinking, road network, indoor community spaces, new housebuilding) but not the change in these assets over time.
- Data on land cover, environmental designations and environmental quality have been calculated at the grid cell level using spatial statistics. Similarly, the estimated ‘accessible’ populations (the number of people resident within 30 minutes of each grid cell) were calculated using grid cell centroids and a travel network

analysis. Novel information on the extent of engagement with natural and cultural ecosystem services was created using geotagged Flickr photographs.

While there are uncertainties in the creation of grid cell-level values, which are associated with ‘downscaling’ and estimation methods, and the quality of forms of location data, the gridded dataset represents novel and valuable information, which is available at a consistent and granular geography. For the analysis contained in this report, population and economic outcomes were reported as percentage changes over time (for example, 2011-22). Changes in outcomes and the accessibility of assets in different types of rural and urban areas have been assessed using descriptive statistics, but for more detailed assessments of the accessibility of assets and their relationships with outcomes, aggregated values for local areas - defined as the grid cells within 20km distance of a central cell – were calculated. Changes in outcomes and access to assets were calculated for these local areas and were expressed as a density per 1,000 people (in 2022) or per km² area, or as another percentage if more appropriate. Not all indicators in Table 1 were included in the aggregated indicators. The form of indicators used and analysis techniques applied are summarised in each section of the report.

Table 1: Indicators representing population and economic outcomes, and rural development assets, calculated at the hexagon grid level.

Category	Variable	Year(s) or period
Population outcome	Accessible population [estimated population within 30 minutes’ travel]	1991, 2001, 2011, 2022
Population outcome	Accessible working age population [estimated population within 30 minutes’ travel]	1991, 2001, 2011, 2022
Population outcome	Total population	1991, 2001, 2011, 2022
Population outcome	Working age population	1991, 2001, 2011, 2022
Population outcome	Dependency ratio [number of likely dependents per 100 people of working age]	1991, 2001, 2011, 2022
Population outcome	Accessible working age population [estimated population within 30 minutes’ travel]	1991, 2001, 2011, 2022
Economic outcome	Number of employed residents [estimated FTEs]	2011, 2022
Economic outcome	Number of businesses	2019, 2025
Economic outcome	Gross Value Added [£ millions]	2001, 2011, 2022
Anchor organisations	Total income of registered charities which operate locally [£]	2019, 2025
Builders and construction resources	Businesses within the building and construction sectors [number]	2019, 2025
Businesses / small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)	Diversity of businesses [Shannon Index]	2019, 2025
Care and health	GP practices [number]	2019, 2025
Care and health	Pharmacies [number]	2019, 2024
Care and health	Optometrists and opticians [number]	2025
Care and health	Beds in care homes for older people [number]	2019, 2025
Care and health	Registered childcare places [number]	2019, 2025
Community and group spaces	Indoor spaces for communities and groups to come together [number]	2025
Digital infrastructure	Properties with fast broadband [%]	2019, 2024
Housing	Area of land under housing construction [m ²]	2020, 2025
Housing	Housing sales [number]	2019, 2023
Housing	Housing sales: market prices [£]	2019, 2023
Landscape, heritage and the natural environment	Index of environmental quality	2014-2022
Landscape, heritage and the natural environment	Area of non-farm rural land cover [m ²]	2023
Landscape, heritage and the natural environment	Engagement with natural and cultural ecosystem services [number of photographs]	2015-2023

Local energy	Capacity of installed renewable energy schemes [MW]	2019, 2024
Local food	Businesses involved in food and drink manufacturing [number]	2019, 2025
Local food	Places for social eating and drinking [number]	2025
Local food	Grocery stores [number]	2019, 2025
Schools and education	Publicly funded primary schools [number]	2019, 2024
Schools and education	Publicly funded secondary schools [number]	2019, 2024
Schools and education	Adults with degree-level qualifications [%]	2011, 2022
Schools and education	Adults with any qualification [%]	2011, 2022
Transport and physical infrastructure	Road network length [km]	2025
Tourism	Businesses within the tourist sector [number]	2019, 2025

Creating a consistent geography for understanding rural Scotland

Measuring and understanding rural economic development in Scotland is affected by the geographical units for which data are published. Data Zones are the key geography used for the dissemination of small area statistics in Scotland. They are aggregates of Census Output Areas and – ideally – are geographically compact units with roughly standard populations (500 to 1,000 residents) which reflect underlying communities¹¹. While Data Zones are spatially detailed (6,976 Data Zones were drawn after the 2011 Census, and 7,392 were produced after the 2022 Census), they have been drawn based on a population threshold and are, as such, more strongly suited to densely populated areas in towns and cities. Rural Data Zones are often large, with uneven boundaries (Flowerdew et al., 2007) which are poorly aligned with islands and communities in remoter areas. The stability of Data Zones between Census years enables the monitoring of change in the same regions over time, although their usefulness for understanding longer-term changes in the economy and society is reduced due to the boundary changes: there have been three different sets of Data Zones produced in 2001, 2011 and 2022.

Across Europe, similar municipalities and regions are regularly used for statistical publishing, with the Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) framework used by Eurostat to classify larger regions, districts and smaller administrative areas for reporting socio-economic information in a consistent way. However, countries and multi-national organisations are increasingly producing socio-economic data in a ‘gridded’ format, where indicators are published for small grid cells. Examples include:

- the EU population and housing census (2021) released at the level of 1km² grid squares by Eurostat¹²
- Census data in Germany¹³ (2022) and France¹⁴ (2021) published for 1km² cells (and 100m cells in Germany)
- the generation of a detailed urban-rural classification in Scandinavia¹⁵ at the 1km² grid level (2024)
- a number of grid-based population datasets have been produced, including the POPGRID¹⁶ and Global Human Settlement Layer¹⁷ initiatives of the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre.

Grid cells have the disadvantage of not, in themselves, representing places or communities. Additionally, the calculation of indicators at the grid cell level, like those described in this report, involves some estimation and uncertainty. Examples include the adjustment of existing data for administrative units (e.g. Census population totals) to grid cells, and the identification and calculation of the locations of facilities and places to aggregate to the cells. However, the gridded approach is highly granular and flexible. The modifiable areal unit problem – the impacts of boundary definition on the measurement of underlying phenomena (Buzzelli et al., 2020) – is arguably reduced

¹¹ <https://www.gov.scot/collections/small-area-statistics/>

¹² https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Population_and_housing_census_2021_-_population_grids

¹³ https://www.zensus2022.de/EN/What-is-the-census/grid_cells_results_2011.html

¹⁴ <https://www.insee.fr/en/metadonnees/source/operation/s2150/presentation>

¹⁵ <https://www.norden.org/en/publication/towards-grid-based-nordic-territorial-typology>

¹⁶ <https://www.popgrid.org/jrc>

¹⁷ <https://human-settlement.emergency.copernicus.eu/datasets.php>

through the consistency of shape and area, and gridded data derived from Census datasets has also been used to analyse social change and developing inequalities in the UK (Patias et al., 2022).

Given these benefits, we decided to draw on the gridded approach and have generated a hexagonal ('hex') grid (cell size: 5km) covering the entire land area of Scotland, for calculating indicators of rural development. The 5km distance provides an approximation of a 'local area', as an adult can cover this distance in an hour of walking¹⁸. In the context of Scotland's highly urbanised population, the grid cells – which are based on area, rather than population – substantially increase the detail which can be measured in rural areas. Although there are fewer hex grid cells (4,529) than Data Zones (7,392), less than c. 30% of the Data Zones (2,120) are classed as rural (based on the Scottish Government's Urban Rural Classification¹⁹). However, 4,327 hex grid cells (approximately 95% of the grid) are defined as rural or 'mostly rural', based on the distribution of the population across the Urban Rural Classification (Table 2).

For the purposes of analysing change in outcomes and development resources in rural Scotland, we have further subdivided the rural and mostly rural grid cells into three categories, reflecting the accessibility of the nearest urban settlement defined in the Urban Rural Classification, and the overall access to people (Table 2). Places where we estimate that less than 10,000 people lived within 30 minutes' travel (in 2022) are defined as sparsely populated areas (SPA) which have a low 'critical mass' for services and economic activities: these areas are associated with vulnerability to population decline²⁰. A five-fold classification of the grid, including the three more detailed rural categories, is shown in Figure 2. In 2022, sparsely populated areas (in common with previous definitions) covered many of the upland, mountainous and island areas of Scotland, but do not include core settlements in remote regions (Stornoway, Wick, Thurso, Kirkwall, Lerwick, Fort William, Oban) or their surroundings.

Table 2: The classification of grid cells into urban and rural areas.

Classification	Description	Number (percentage of all cells)
Urban	100% of the population in the grid cell lived within urban areas (large or other urban areas with a population above 10,000 people)	9 (0.2)
mostly Urban	More of the population lived in urban areas, than lived in rural areas or small towns.	193 (4.3)
mostly Rural	More of the population lived in rural areas or small towns, than lived in urban areas.	58 (1.3)
Rural	100% of the population lived within rural areas or small towns	4,269 (94.3)
Total	% of all grid cells	4,529 (100)
Accessible Rural	Rural or mostly Rural cells where more of the population lived in accessible places – those within 30 minutes' travel of an urban area, than lived in remote places. These cells are not defined as sparsely populated, as at least 10,000 people lived within 30 minutes.	1,080 (23.8)
Remote Rural	Rural or mostly Rural cells where more of the population lived in remote places – those over 30 minutes from an urban area, than lived in accessible places. These cells are not sparsely populated.	985 (21.7)
Remote Rural - SPA	Rural or mostly Rural cells where more of the population lived in remote place, than lived in accessible places, which are also defined as sparsely populated. Additionally, 24 'accessible' grid cells	2,262 (49.9)

¹⁸ 5km/hr⁻¹ is considered by Transport for London to be a fast walking speed: see

<https://tfl.gov.uk/corporate/transparency/freedom-of-information/foi-request-detail?referenceld=FOI-0318-2526>

¹⁹ <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-government-urban-rural-classification-2022/>

²⁰ <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/sites/default/files/files/research/srp2016-21/RD3.4.1%20Note%20WP1-3%20web%20-%20published.pdf>

which are also sparsely populated are included in this category.

Figure 2: Map showing urban, mostly urban, and three categories of rural grid cells.

The 'big picture' of rural development in Scotland: using grid cells to chart changes in key demographic and economic outcomes

Demographic indicators calculated for the 1991-2022 period (Table 3) emphasise the increasingly urgent population challenges facing more remote and sparsely populated rural areas of Scotland. The total population and working age population of these areas has declined in all three 'intra-Census' periods (1991-2001, 2001-2011, 2011-22). Conversely, the population of accessible rural areas has increased in all three of these periods, but the rate of increase slowed from 2001-11 (+6.5%) to 2011-22 (+2.3%).

For all regions of Scotland, demographic change has turned more negative in 2011-22, compared with the previous decade. Rural populations are also becoming rapidly more imbalanced. Working age populations declined from 2011-22 in all types of rural areas, and dependency ratios have sharply increased: in 2022, all types of rural area had approximately ten more dependents per 100 people of working age, than was the case in 2011. This is a major shift compared with previous decades, where dependency ratios changed very little. This change has exacerbated the existing uneven population structures, as remote rural areas (and sparsely populated remote areas) had more than 70 dependents per 100 people of working age in 2022, a higher ratio than in accessible rural areas, and in urban areas.

Changes in the accessible population – the estimated number of people living within 30 minutes' travel from each grid cell - reinforce these findings. The mean accessible population for accessible rural grid cells increased by 12,940 people over this period, but the averages declined for remote rural (-333 people) and remote and sparsely populated rural cells (-30 people). This represents a fall in the 'critical mass' which is readily available to support economic activities and services, which presents a challenge for the sustainability and resilience of communities. Considering the accessible population which is of working age, the average figures for urban and mostly urban grid cells grew by 15,579 and 7,506 people, respectively, between 2011 and 2022. By contrast, the average accessible working age population fell in all types of rural areas over the same period, with the largest fall (-1,633 people) in remote rural areas.

Two key economic indicators - the total employment level and number of businesses - show the highly spatially concentrated pattern of economic activity in Scotland, as large majorities of employed people (73%) and businesses (80%) are found in urban areas, and employment in remote rural areas fell between 2011 and 2022. The number of registered businesses also grew in all types of areas from 2019 to 2025, with the most positive trend (c. +37%) observed in remote, sparsely populated areas.

Table 3: Economic and demographic change in Scotland. Summary statistics exclude values for grid cells which had never been populated from 1991 to 2022.

	Total population, 2022	2011-22 (%)	2001-11 (%)	1991-2001 (%)	Working age population, 2022	2011-22 (%)	2001-11 (%)	1991-2001 (%)
Urban	463,139	7.8	11.8	10.5	355,416	7.6	17.9	19.0
mostly Urban	3,521,315	2.8	3.4	-0.2	2,239,541	-0.5	5.1	-0.1
Accessible Rural	1,103,901	2.3	6.5	3.9	659,828	-3.7	5.9	3.9
Remote Rural	255,760	-2.9	4.2	-1.4	148,811	-8.8	3.7	-1.9
Remote Rural - SPA	95,979	-1.7	-0.2	-2.7	55,197	-7.8	-0.7	-3.1
All rural areas	1,455,639	1.1	5.6	2.4	863,836	-4.9	5.0	2.3
	Dependency ratio*, 2022	2011-22 (people)	2001-11 (people)	1991-2001 (people)	Employment (FTEs), 2022	2011-22 (%)	Businesses, 2025	2019-25 (%)
Urban	30.3	0.2	-7.1	-10.5	207,438	9.4	83,755	23.4
mostly Urban	57.2	5.0	-2.6	-0.2	1,459,736	6.0	132,313	25.4

Accessible Rural	67.3	9.8	0.9	0.0	459,502	1.8	41,560	17.5
Remote Rural	71.9	10.3	0.8	0.9	103,546	-3.2	9,362	18.4
Remote Rural - SPA	73.9	10.6	0.8	0.6	40,025	-0.7	3,981	36.9
All rural areas	68.5	9.9	0.9	0.2	603,073	0.7	54,903	18.9

Totals rounded to nearest whole number, all other figures to one decimal place. *The number of likely dependents (children and people of older age) per 100 working age people.

The extent of the sparsely populated areas where less than 10,000 people lived within 30 minutes' drive - in 2022 - is shown on Figure 3. The SPAs covered 45.4% of Scotland (35,355 km²) in this year. This is a slight increase from 2011, where 45.3% of Scotland was sparsely populated, compared with 46.0% (2001) and 46.4% (1991). Although the SPAs have been relatively stable in area, the shrinking from 1991 to 2011 reflects a positive demographic trend in some remoter areas, and the slight expansion from 2011-2022 is a reversal of this. A mapping of the change in the accessible population from 2011 to 2022 (Figure 4) demonstrates fast growth (measured using the 'raw' number of people) in and around the Central Belt, in Aberdeenshire, near Inverness, and on the Orkney Mainland. Larger declines in the number of accessible people have been observed in more isolated regions of the country, including most of the south west, the far north, parts of Argyll and Moray, and in Shetland and the Western Isles. These are 'broad brush' trends, however, as the detailed gridded data reveals considerable diversity in rural areas, particularly in the west of Scotland - for example, the accessible populations increased in many parts of Mull, Skye and Lochaber, in contrast with more negative trends in nearby areas (for example, Islay, Arran and Cowal). The growing population imbalance in many remote and sparsely populated rural areas is shown by the change in the dependency ratios from 2011-22 (Figure 5). These data are summaries of areas 'local' to each grid cell (within a 20km distance), and show that the number of likely dependents relative to the number of working age residents has increased across the vast majority of Scotland, but with particularly large increases in remoter and upland areas of Scotland, including the west coast and Hebrides. Rural areas where the dependency ratio has decreased or remained relatively stable - signifying a healthier population structure - are concentrated in the Central Belt and near Dundee, and also in regions near some remote towns (Fort William, Oban, Campbeltown, Thurso).

Understanding the development challenges faced by rural areas requires a longitudinal perspective, to understand the duration and persistence of these issues, as well as the magnitude of very recent change. Figure 6 visualises the number of intra-Census periods between 1991 and 2022 where local populations have increased, and where dependency ratios have increased. The local areas where demographic changes have been most consistently positive since 1991 - experiencing multiple increases in population, and few increases in the dependency ratio - are shown in more vivid green colours. These are distributed across the east of central Scotland around Edinburgh, in more accessible areas around Inverness and Aberdeen, in the mainlands of Orkney and Shetland, and notably in Skye, Lochalsh and around Oban in the west. More long-running population challenges - multiple population declines and increases in the dependency ratio - are apparent in the remote south and west near Stranraer, Girvan and Campbeltown, in the far north and the Cairngorms, and in more isolated island regions.

The maps of two key economic indicators: the changes in local employment as full-time equivalents (Figure 7) and the total number of local businesses (Figure 8) show indicators covering overlapping time periods (2011-22 and 2019-25, respectively). The geographical distribution of employment change shows some similarities, and some notable differences, with that of the accessible population change (Figure 4). There are two main geographical regions where growth in employment has been concentrated: firstly, across the Central Belt and its outlying regions, extending into the Scottish Borders and into Perth and Kinross and Angus. Secondly, the area running from (roughly) Inverness to the west coast around Kyle of Lochalsh, Fort William, and Oban, several islands of Highland and Argyll and Bute, and parts of the Western Isles. The data near Aberdeen and in the north east of Scotland suggests stable or declining local employment. The pattern of change in the number of registered businesses (Figure 8) shows, similarly, a weaker trend in the Aberdeenshire than in most other parts of Scotland, where the number of businesses has grown considerably.

Figure 3: The accessible population of hex grid cells, 2022. Sparsely populated areas (SPAs) are shown in shades of blue.

Figure 4: The change in the accessible population of hex grid cells, 2011-22.

Figure 5: Change in the dependency ratio of the local population (within 20km of each hex grid cell), 2011-22.

Figure 6: Summary of changes in the local population (within 20km of each hex grid cell), showing the number of periods between Census years where the population and dependency ratio increased, 1991-2022.

Figure 7: Change in employment (full-time equivalents) in the local area (within 20km of each hex grid cell), 2011-22.

Figure 8: Change in the number of businesses in the local area (within 20km of each hex grid cell), 2019-25.

Using grid cells to understand the changing distribution of economic assets supporting rural development

Understanding rural development opportunities in rural Scotland requires consideration of the distribution of economic assets across the country. As mentioned in the introduction to this report, our selection of the assets – or development resources - to focus on was informed by a consultation with rural stakeholders and practitioners in 2023, contributing to an ‘inventory’ of priorities²¹ which are relevant to supporting a wellbeing economy.

Acknowledging the very broad range of factors which can contribute to wellbeing and which support economic activity in places, the categories of assets reflect essential and universal services, natural and cultural capital, businesses within priority growth sectors for Scotland as a whole, and services which enable wider economic participation (for example, ultrafast broadband and childcare).

The distribution of economic resources across different areas

The fine-grained grid level data enables us to assess the evenness of the current distribution of these economic resources across different types of rural and urban areas (Table 4), and how this has changed – either since the last Scottish Census, or across the COVID-19 period until the present (Table 5), in cases where high quality data are available to enable this comparison to be made.

When compared with the population distribution - the proportion of Scotland’s population in each type of area - spatial inequalities in asset distributions are clear (Table 4). Many of these are as expected, with natural and cultural capital concentrated in remoter rural areas – for example, over 60% of Flickr photographs reflecting engagement with natural and cultural capital were in remote rural areas, as is the vast majority of non-agricultural countryside. Business registrations in key sectors for Scotland’s economy, and the average diversity of businesses (based on the industry sectors) are over-represented in urban centres, while more than two-thirds of all beds in care homes for older people, and childcare places, are found within the wider ‘mostly Urban’ areas.

Interestingly, for some essential healthcare services (pharmacies and GP practices), third sector and community resources (locally operating charity income and community spaces), places for purchasing food and drink (grocery stores and places for social eating and drinking) and some key business sectors (tourism and food manufacturing), both parts of urban areas and remote rural areas have more resources than may be expected by their population levels. These findings reflect two phenomena: the concentration of high proportions of Scotland’s population and economic resources in cities and large towns, and the fact that remoter rural areas ‘punch above their weight’ in the availability of some resources. Given the large geographical area covered by remoter and sparsely populated rural areas, this should not be confused with straightforward access to these resources – but the relatively high numbers of (for example) grocery stores, GP practices and social infrastructure is, in some ways, an under-recognised strength of these areas.

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8121405>

Table 4: The distribution of current (i.e. the most recent year for each indicator) economic assets across Scotland.

Category	Indicator	Year	Urban	mostly Urban	Acc. Rural	Rem. Rural	Rem. Rural - SPA
Data: the percentage of total assets within the type of area across Scotland. Bold text shows where this figure is higher than expected, based on the population distribution in 2022.							
	<i>Total population</i>	2022	8.5	64.7	20.3	4.7	1.8
Anchor organisations	Total income of registered charities which operate locally	2025	25.5	54.1	10.2	6.6	3.6
Builders and construction resources	Businesses within the building and construction sectors	2025	15.9	59.2	19.0	4.4	1.5
Care and health	Beds in care homes for older people	2025	6.4	68.8	18.9	5.1	0.9
Care and health	Pharmacies	2024	8.5	58.5	21.2	7.5	4.3
Care and health	GP practices	2025	9.1	58.5	18.9	7.8	5.6
Care and health	Optometrists and opticians	2025	18.7	61.5	13.5	4.6	1.7
Care and health	Registered childcare places	2025	7.5	67.3	19.9	3.9	1.4
Community and group spaces	Indoor spaces for communities and groups to come together	2025	9.4	42.7	27.1	11.6	9.2
Housing	Area of land under housing construction	2025	2.5	61.2	32.7	2.9	0.8
Housing	Housing sales	2023	11.2	64.0	19.5	3.7	1.6
Landscape, heritage and the natural environment	Area of non-farm rural land cover	2023	0.0	1.5	15.7	22.8	60.1
Landscape, heritage and the natural environment	Engagement with natural and cultural capital	2015-23	0.0	8.1	30.1	20.8	41.0
Local energy	Capacity of installed renewable energy schemes	2024	0.1	9.0	36.6	20.1	34.2
Local food	Grocery stores	2025	13.8	58.4	16.8	6.1	4.9
Local food	Places for social eating and drinking	2025	26.1	43.3	15.9	7.8	6.9
Local food	Businesses involved in food and drink manufacturing	2025	22.1	43.4	21.4	6.8	6.2
Schools and education	Publicly funded primary schools	2024	3.7	50.1	29.9	9.2	7.2
Schools and education	Publicly funded secondary schools	2024	4.1	62.3	17.9	8.3	7.4
Transport and physical infrastructure	Road network length	2025	1.9	28.9	39.7	17.1	12.4
Tourism	Businesses within the tourist sector	2025	27.8	49.8	14.4	4.9	3.1
Data: averages (means)							
Businesses / SMEs	Diversity of businesses (Shannon Index)	2025	1.9	2.1	1.6	1.1	0.9
Digital infrastructure	Properties with fast broadband (%)	2024	89.6	81.6	37.4	24.0	12.5
Housing	Housing sales: market prices (£)	2023	232,329	217,992	341,876	325,517	309,360
Landscape, heritage and the natural environment	Index of environmental quality (mean)	2014-22	1.7	2.6	3.7	4.6	5.4
Schools and education	Adults with degree-level qualifications (%)	2022	44.1	30.0	36.4	33.2	32.1
Schools and education	Adults with any qualification (%)	2022	87.8	83.2	86.6	86.8	90.9

Change in the distribution of economic resources across different areas

Where change in the number, extent, or quality of assets can be reliably analysed, either between the last two Censuses (2011-22) or the pre- to post-COVID-19 emergency period (2019-2025), an uneven pattern emerges (Table 5). Although the number of registered businesses has increased in all types of areas, the number of businesses in the key sectors of construction, food and drink manufacturing, and tourism, have grown most quickly in remote and sparsely populated areas. Figure 9 shows grid cells where the number of food and drink businesses has changed between 2019-25, and cells where access to these businesses within the local area (defined as a 20km distance) has changed in the same period. This shows a more complex pattern than the broader trends across the five types of rural and urban areas, but suggests growth and strength in this sector in many rural areas, alongside concentrated business growth in urban areas of central Scotland. In the north east of Scotland, there is a contrast between declining business numbers in some parts of northern Aberdeenshire (a traditional farming and fishing region) and more consistent growth in the west of Aberdeenshire and Speyside.

Other economic resources – renewable energy schemes, grocery stores, high-speed internet access and house prices - have increased throughout Scotland, but most quickly in mostly urban or accessible rural areas (Table 5). A map of the places where renewable energy capacity has changed from 2019-24: either within grid cells or in their local surroundings (Figure 10) emphasises expansion in this capacity across many parts of Scotland, with concentrations of growth in the upland areas of the south west, the Lothians, northern Aberdeenshire and inland Moray, and in some remoter areas (northern Skye, Argyll, and near Wick). These increases are likely to be associated with major windfarm developments, including (for example) the major Clyde and Beattock schemes. The planning restrictions on windfarms in the (often remote) National Scenic Areas has influenced the fast rates of growth in mostly urban and accessible rural regions.

By contrast, the extent of essential care and healthcare resources has declined in most area types in Scotland – but within rural areas, these declines have been particularly high in remote rural and sparsely populated areas (Table 5). For numbers of primary schools, all types of rural areas have seen a net closure of primary schools, but the largest decline in school numbers has been in remote rural areas (-6.6% from 2019-24) closely followed by remote and sparsely populated rural (-6.0%). Mapping (Figure 11) emphasises the geographically uneven nature of these changes – with numbers of primary schools increasing close to Glasgow and Edinburgh, and in Orkney, but declining in several rural areas. The more detailed spatial distribution of changes in GP practices (Figure 12) and registered childcare places (Figure 13) are very different – with relative stability in GP practice numbers across most of Scotland, but with concentrations of declines in more populated areas of Scotland and in some islands (Islay, Mull). The pattern of changing access to childcare is much more uneven and complex.

For most economic assets, the wider trends by area type (Table 4) and more granular mapping of gridded data suggest that changes in the extent of these development resources have rarely followed a straightforward urban-rural divide. These changes are likely to reflect multiple processes, including long-term budget constraints on public services, the impacts of declining and aging populations on demand for public services, and the challenges of improving infrastructure in remoter rural areas.

Table 5: Change in economic assets in recent years.

Category	Indicator	Year(s)	Urban	mostly Urban	Acc. Rural	Rem. Rural	Rem. Rural - SPA
Data: percentage change in totals							
Anchor organisations	Total income of registered charities which operate locally	2019-25	1.0	-2.1	4.2	2.8	3.4
Builders and construction resources	Businesses within the building and construction sectors	2019-25	26.9	27.7	24.2	13.9	45.3
Care and health	Beds in care homes for older people	2019-25	-1.4	-1.7	-1.7	1.8	-33.9
Care and health	Pharmacies	2019-24	-5.0	-1.0	-0.7	-1.0	-6.5
Care and health	GP practices	2019-25	-12.0	-4.9	-5.1	-6.8	-7.4
Care and health	Registered childcare places	2019-25	-5.9	0.6	-1.1	-2.4	-5.2
Housing	Housing sales	2019-23	2.0	-14.8	-14.5	10.7	8.7
Local energy	Capacity of installed renewable energy schemes	2019-24		205.6	72.1	54.7	37.6
Local food	Grocery stores	2019-25	23.4	25.5	17.6	20.4	13.0
Local food	Businesses involved in food and drink manufacturing	2019-25	28.6	35.7	25.9	25.2	50.0
Schools and education	Publicly funded primary schools	2019-24	2.8	0.4	-3.9	-6.6	-6.0
Schools and education	Publicly funded secondary schools	2019-24	0.0	2.3	-1.5	0.0	0.0
Tourism	Businesses within the tourist sector	2019-25	31.2	49.0	48.3	48.3	63.3
Data: raw change in average (mean) value							
Businesses / SMEs	Diversity of businesses (Shannon Index)	2019-25	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1
Digital infrastructure	Properties with fast broadband (%)	2019-24	39.0	35.8	33.0	22.3	11.1
Housing	Housing sales: market prices (£)	2019-23	11,483	31,790	36,293	19,170	26,272
Schools and education	Adults with degree-level qualifications (%)	2011-22	7.5	5.7	5.5	5.4	6.0
Schools and education	Adults with any qualification (%)	2011-22	8.3	9.9	9.0	9.7	9.0

Figure 9: Map showing grid cells where the number of businesses involved in food and drink manufacturing has changed, or where accessibility in the local area (within 20km) has changed (2019-25)

Figure 10: Map showing grid cells where renewable energy capacity (in MW) has changed, or where this capacity has changed in the local area (within 20km) (2019-24)

Figure 11: Map showing grid cells where the number of primary schools has changed, or where accessibility in the local area (within 20km) has changed (2019-24)

Figure 12: Map showing grid cells where the number of GP practices has changed, or where accessibility in the local area (within 20km) has changed (2019-25)

Figure 13: Map showing grid cells where the number of childcare places has changed, or where accessibility in the local area (within 20km) has changed (2019-25)

Understanding rural diversity: identifying themes of economic assets

In order to improve our understanding of the diversity of rural Scotland, and to provide insights into the economic development opportunities which are available in different places, we have summarised the variation in access to economic assets into five underlying themes. A statistical method - exploratory factor analysis – was applied to a set of variables representing the accessibility of assets within a 20km distance of each grid cell. For most variables this accessibility was estimated as the number, extent or value of assets per 1,000 people, based on the total population living within the same distance of the grid cell. Some other indicators which reflect land use or land-based assets were expressed as a density (per square kilometre), while others were an appropriate percentage (for example, the percentage of premises with access to ultrafast broadband).

The factors are summarised in Table 6 and are given descriptive labels based on the types of variables which correlate with them, and they form key themes which reflect similar types of economic resources. The 'Everyday economy' factor appears to reflect access to frequently used health and education facilities, places producing or retailing food, and social infrastructure (community spaces); these indicators correspond with the essential infrastructure and services within the foundational economy (e.g. Crisp et al, 2024: 1014). However, the distribution of grid cells which score highly on this factor (Figure 14) are not, as might be expected, concentrated in accessible areas with high numbers of resources, but in remoter rural areas along the west coast, with very high values in some smaller islands (for example, Rum and Fair Isle). High values, therefore, reflect a large number of these services and assets relative to the size of the population, rather than the total number of services – a characteristic of 'over-representation' also noted in the asset distributions summarised above (Table 4).

The 'Attractive and vibrant' factor appears to reflect recreation, tourism and natural and cultural capital, plus economic vibrancy as business- and education-related indicators correlate positively with the factor. Higher scores are observed across the west coast and in several islands and across mountainous areas of northern Scotland, with high values also visible close to Edinburgh (Figure 15).

The 'New build' factor corresponds with housing construction and high connectivity in more accessible rural areas, and the geographical distribution of higher values (Figure 16) confirms this.

The fourth factor is labelled 'Care' as variables related to childcare, care homes, healthcare and third sector income correlate positively with it. The spatial distribution of scores for this factor (Figure 17) seems to reflect the tendency for some of these services to be over-represented in both urban and remote rural areas (Table 4) as values are high in some remoter areas - in the west of Scotland, and in parts of the northern and western isles, and areas close to urban areas and larger towns also have higher scores.

Finally, the 'Clean energy' factor is labelled as such because renewable energy capacity correlates most strongly with it, and the scores (Figure 18) are high in areas of major energy production, including the Ayrshire and Lanarkshire region and some parts of Shetland.

Table 6: Summary factors which underpin the accessibility of economic assets. Analysis based on most recent data available.

Factor	Positive correlations with factor	Negative correlations with factor
Factor 1 – “ Everyday economy ”	Publicly funded primary schools Grocery stores GP practices Businesses involved in food and drink manufacturing Indoor spaces for communities and groups to come together	Beds in care homes for older people
Factor 2 – “ Attractive and vibrant ”	Adults with degree-level qualifications Businesses within the tourist sector Engagement with natural and cultural capital Places for social eating and drinking Area of non-farm rural land cover Businesses within the building and construction sectors Housing sales	
Factor 3 – “ New build ”	Area of land under housing construction Properties with fast broadband	Area of non-farm rural land cover
Factor 4 – “ Care ”	Registered childcare places Businesses within the building and construction sectors Optometrists and opticians Beds in care homes for older people Total income of registered charities which operate locally	
Factor 5 – “ Clean energy ”	Properties with fast broadband Capacity of installed renewable energy schemes Housing sales	

Note: Collectively these factors explain 43% of variance, with factors presented in order of importance.

Figure 14: 'Everyday economy' score for rural grid cells

Figure 15: 'Attractive and vibrant' score for rural grid cells

Figure 16: 'New build' score for rural grid cells

Figure 17: 'Care' score for rural grid cells

Figure 18: 'Clean energy' score for rural grid cells

Correlations between factors

As the indicators included in the analysis described above were chosen to represent assets which support a wellbeing economy, it could be argued that places scoring well for all five factors have particularly high economic potential. However, the moderate negative correlations between some of these factor scores (Figure 19) show that some themes do not typically occur or cluster together. The 'Everyday economy' and 'Attractive and vibrant' factors are negatively correlated with 'New build' and 'Clean energy', suggesting that the relative over-representation of foundational economic resources, and areas associated with recreation, tourism and considerable environmental value are unlikely to co-occur with places where expansion of new, well connected housing is taking place, or clusters of renewable energy generation. The very weak correlation between 'Everyday economy' and 'Care' is notable, as these factors are conceptually quite closely related: the theme of relatively high access to some essential services does not necessarily extend to the caring services more likely to be provided by the private sector, and voluntary activities. Positive correlations between 'New build' and the 'Care' and 'Clean energy' factors suggests some overlaps in the distributions of these types of assets and multi-functionality.

Figure 19: Correlations between factors in rural areas

Which types of assets and changes in assets best predict local outcomes? An in-depth look at working age population and employment change

Finally, we provide insights into the factors which are associated with two development outcomes in contrasting types of rural area in Scotland: accessible areas and remote, sparsely populated areas. We measured accessibility of assets using the five dimensions identified above, and change in the density of assets (either per 1,000 people, or per square kilometre) in the periods available - all indicators were calculated for local areas (20km distance).

The directions of significant predictors of the outcomes are summarised in Table 7. Although none of the five dimensions reflecting recent accessibility of assets are significant predictors for all four regressions, it is notable that the pattern of significant predictors suggests that assets reflecting 'Care' - correlating positively with current access to childcare and care homes, and the third sector, has a consistent positive association with the economic and demographic outcomes, particularly in remote rural areas. This is supported by the positive effects of change in access to care for older people in all regressions, and the positive effect of charity income in remote areas. As these types of services often reflect private and third sector provision, they are potentially less universally accessible than public healthcare services, and therefore may have a strong influence on the size of the working age and employed populations.

It is interesting to note that growth in tourism businesses is a positive predictor of working age population change and employment growth in remote rural areas, but is a negative predictor in accessible rural areas. The 'Attractive and vibrant' dimension is not, however, a positive predictor of outcome growth in remote and sparsely populated areas. Potentially, this suggests that growth in tourist activity which is grounded in rural places (in other words, growth in the number of businesses based in rural places) has a positive effect in remote and sparsely populated rural areas, rather than the presence of tourist activity in attractive areas by itself. Furthermore, growth in food and drink businesses have a positive effect on working age population change in remote and sparsely populated areas, only. Taken together with the positive effect of change in tourist businesses, these suggest the benefits of locally-based activities in more remote areas and support the wider importance of private sector employment in this type of rural area. Potentially, this supports the principles of community wealth building which emphasise the local, non-extractive circulation of money (e.g. Crisp et al., 2024: 1215). Interestingly, growing access to schools and fast broadband are positive predictors of outcomes in accessible areas, only.

For other services, it is notable that the 'Everyday economy' dimension is positively associated with working age population change in accessible rural areas, but is negatively associated in remote and sparsely populated areas. As this dimension reflects a high number of everyday resources relative to the size of the local population, the situation of relatively high numbers of assets in sparsely populated rural areas does not appear to have a positive effect on rural development, as there may be more meaningful barriers to accessing these services – there is, conversely, a positive effect in accessible rural areas. Growth in the population of adults with degree level qualifications is a consistent positive predictor in all regressions. This may reflect a greater tendency for more educated people to move for work, or the tendency of highly skilled jobs to be more resilient over time. In terms of the other consistent positive predictors, it is easy to imagine a positive feedback loop between growth in populations and employment levels, housing sales and construction businesses, although causation cannot be identified from this analysis, and there are overlaps in the time periods for the indicators.

Table 7: Summary of linear regression analyses, indicating significant predictors of the working age population change and the direction of the association. Predictors included within the models: underlying themes of recent access to economic assets (green shading), and change in the density of assets over time (blue shading). All indicators were calculated for local areas within 20km distance of a grid cell.

Outcomes	Working age population change (%), 2011-22		Employment (FTE) change (%), 2011-22	
	Accessible	Remote – SPA	Accessible	Remote – SPA
Rural area type				
Working age population, 2011	+			
Employment (FTE), 2011				
‘Everyday economy’	+	-		
‘Attractive and vibrant’			+	
‘New build’	-	+		+
‘Care’	+	+		+
‘Clean energy’		+	+	-
Total income of registered charities which operate locally (2019-25)	-	+	-	+
Businesses within the building and construction sectors (2019-25)	+	+	+	+
Beds in care homes for older people (2019-25)	+	+	+	+
GP practices (2019-25)		-		-
Registered childcare places (2019-25)	-		-	
Properties with fast broadband (2019-24)	+	-	+	
Housing sales (2019-23)	+	+	+	+
Capacity of installed renewable energy schemes (2019-24)		-		
Grocery stores (2019-25)	-		-	
Businesses involved in food and drink manufacturing (2019-25)		+		
Publicly funded primary schools (2019-24)	+		+	
Publicly funded secondary schools (2019-24)	+		+	
Adults with degree-level qualifications (2011-22)	+	+	+	+
Adults with any qualification (2011-22)	-	-	+	
Businesses within the tourist sector (2019-25)	-	+	-	+

Note: regression models explain 60.0%, 40.6%, 64.6% and 29.4% of variance, respectively. Directions area only shown for significant predictors.

Summary and reflections

In this report we have presented the results of a detailed analysis of mixed datasets which has generated a suite of indicators for measuring changing patterns of rural development outcomes associated with demographic and economic change, and corresponding changes in the accessibility of multi-dimensional assets which can underpin this development. Following this, broader concepts which correlate with access to multiple types of assets have provided new insights into rural inequalities, alongside the mapping of changes in exemplar assets. The regression analyses, considering spatial variability in the access to assets, have identified potential predictors of working age population change and employment change for accessible, and remote and sparsely populated, rural areas.

These analyses are subject to some uncertainty - in particular, the overlapping time periods (a function of the availability of reliable and granular input datasets) raise questions over the causal directions between outcomes and predictors. Similarly, analytical processes which were used to create the hexagonal grid-level database are subject to some uncertainties, including the 'downscaling' of data available for other geographical units (e.g. Data Zones), and the identification of the locations of facilities and services using postcode and settlement information. However, the resulting database and gridded geography contribute significantly to the understanding of recent rural socio-economic change and emerging spatial inequalities. The more detailed multivariate analyses can be refined in future and our plan is to use the indicator database as the basis for understanding socio-economic performance in rural areas, following past geographical research at the James Hutton Institute which has informed funding approaches for LEADER and for community-led local development²², partly based on socio-economic development.

The spatially detailed and longitudinal perspective on demographic change - using data from past Censuses back to 1991 - has emphasised the accelerating population challenges faced by rural Scotland and especially many of its remoter and sparsely populated areas. There is evidence of growth in the accessible population - the 'critical mass' that can support economies and communities - in some remoter coastal and island areas in the west of Scotland and on the Orkney Mainland, and longer-term changes suggest positive demographic trends in these places. However, in other remote rural and island communities - particularly in the south west and far north, and in remoter parts of Argyll and the western Isles, the analysis suggests entrenched demographic challenges. Given the recommendation for place-based and locally-delivered approaches to population decline²³, our analysis supports the need for the design of very different policy approaches - and policy targets - across rural Scotland. These should be driven by the magnitude of recent population shifts - particularly in the accessible population - and the persistence of population declines and negative changes in the population balance, and also the changes taking place in economic indicators in the same locations, including changes in employment and numbers of businesses.

Secondly, the distribution of economic assets across rural Scotland - and changes in these across the last 15 years - show diverse patterns. When compared with the distribution of population in 2022, the tendency for some types of resources to be over-represented in both urban and remote rural areas is particularly notable - this is the case, for example, for grocery stores, tourism businesses and some health and care services. However, it does not appear that this 'over-representation' of services in remoter rural areas - potentially reflecting low numbers of services, scattered settlement patterns and low populations - is a predictor of more positive outcomes. The form of recent changes in the extent of these economic resources varies, with more widespread declines in the extent of care and health resources, and declines in the numbers of schools across rural areas.

This analysis, and the mapping of changes in exemplar assets, raises a critical question over how accessibility to assets and services can, or should best be, measured in rural areas. The aggregation of gridded data into 20km 'local areas', based on a distance matrix which approximates connectivity between the grid cells, and subsequent calculation of population or area densities, reflects a pragmatic approach that minimises numbers of missing values. It also aligns with a similar approach for Data Zone-level data in the Highlands and Islands (Hopkins et al., 2024). However, it has been long recognised that there are multiple ways of measuring accessibility (Pirie, 1979) and yet there is no consistent approach to the ways that these spatial statistics are calculated. Measuring meaningful access

²² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7418862>

²³ <https://www.gov.scot/publications/supporting-enabling-sustainable-communities-action-plan-address-depopulation/>

to services in rural areas - particularly in countries such as Scotland with highly urbanised populations, and where digital delivery of services and activities is increasing - remains a key challenge.

The underlying factors which represent groups or themes of similar assets have provided a visualisation of rural diversity and the different geographies associated with these assets. The surprising distribution of the 'Everyday economy' theme in more remote parts of Scotland reinforces the importance of considering how access to services is measured - particularly given recognition of the foundational economy and community wealth building development approaches, which emphasise local access to services and local circulation of wealth. More broadly, the spatial distributions of high scores for 'Everyday economy', 'Attractive and vibrant', 'New build', 'Care', and 'Clean energy' are very different with a mixed pattern of correlations, emphasising the limited co-occurrence of these development opportunities in the same places. Further refinement and investigation of these factors, and their spatial overlaps, could be a valuable next step.

Finally, the regression analyses have identified significant predictors of key outcomes, change in the working age and employed populations, for contrasting types of rural areas. While these should be interpreted with caution, they point to the positive effects of economic resources representing care and differences in the resource types, and changes in resources, affecting outcomes in accessible and remote and sparsely populated rural areas.

We suggest that using an 'assets' approach to understand rural economic opportunities has, alongside a granular and consistent measurement approach for these assets, proved to be useful in identifying emerging development opportunities and inequalities in Scotland. Inevitably there are uncertainties and limitations in an analysis which takes place at the national scale and in underlying datasets used, and we recognise the requirement for further refinement and discussion of these results. However, at a time when rural areas are undergoing a transition to a lower-carbon economy and are experiencing longer-term population challenges and high inequalities – raising the possibility of a rise in 'green discontent' (Rodríguez-Pose and Bartalucci, 2024), we hope that this analysis can support the targeting and design of positive interventions.

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Appendix: data sources and software used in indicator calculation and analysis

The vast majority of data used in this work was sourced from openly licensed and freely available resources, often available under the [Open Government License](#). In addition, data on housing sales were provided by RightMove. We acknowledge the following producers, publishers and providers of data:

Analytical software, including R packages

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Census or official geographies and classifications

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Spatial data sources only used on maps

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Health services data

Public Health Scotland Primary Care Team GP Practice Contact Details and List Sizes: GP Practices and List sizes January 2025. UK Open Government Licence (OGL).

Public Health Scotland Primary Care Team GP Practice Contact Details and List Sizes: GP Practices and List sizes January 2019. UK Open Government Licence (OGL).

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Public Health Scotland Prescribing Team Dispenser Location Contact Details: Dispenser Details January 2019. UK Open Government Licence (OGL)

Public Health Scotland Dental Care Team Dental Practices and Patient Registrations: Dental Practices September 2024. UK Open Government Licence (OGL)

Public Health Scotland Dental Care Team Dental Practices and Patient Registrations: Dental Practices March 2019. UK Open Government Licence (OGL)

Care services data

Care Inspectorate Datastore (as at 31 January 2025) Excel with Pivots. Contains public sector information licensed under the Open Government Licence v3.0. <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/>

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Datasets used to calculate index of environmental quality

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Economic data

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Office for National Statistics Business Register and Employment Survey : open access (Data: 2019, 2023). ONS Crown Copyright Reserved [from Nomis on 16 March 2025]

Other data providers

Flickr API. Data accessed via photosearcher R package (Nathan Fox, Tom August, Francesca Mancini, Katherine E. Parks, Felix Eigenbrod, James M. Bullock, Louis Sutter, Laura J. Graham, 'photosearcher' package in R: An accessible and reproducible method for harvesting large datasets from Flickr, SoftwareX, Volume 12, 2020, 100624,ISSN 2352-7110, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2020.100624>).

RightMove.